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Physiological Vehicle Dynamics as Space technology in the Universe

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ABSTRACT

The levitation of one sky species into another zenith or upper sky level or other lower sky or nadir sky level is as important as in the case of space technology before and after the life of human beings. In the ancient Ramayan, King Ram has enchanted bhootas for pick and place to lower the sky of dead persons as soldiers. Here the vehicle itself acts as a physiological vehicle acting as dynamics. In modern days also, after human death, the body of one of its sheaths has been picked and placed at its native sky level; it may be lower sky or upper sky. You can visibly see a bhoota only if there will be sense-level sex; otherwise, you can't see. This paper discusses how the sheath layer of the human body gets the dynamics in the entire universe. The main technology about this is quantum engineering and space technology. The lower sky as the bottommost is the ghost, and there the vehicle is different; usually made up of sense-level tamarind tree material, it is present. This is used for levitation. Not only these lower sky, also asura vehicle is different. In the upper sky, the vehicle for levitation purposes from one sky to another is made as a case of Airavat.

Keywords: *Zenith, nadir, positive and negative species, Bhoota, vehicle dynamics, levitation*

INTRODUCTION

Through chemistry, as chemicals are mainly responsible for stable and unstable levitation of the human body sheath or soul. In these cases, underwear politics as sex through all kinds of levitation would be getting to that instant of time. But this is a victory of lust only, but from dharma one can levitate the human body from the planet Earth to the 1st sky by a direct way without any kind of sense-level touch like sex. This is from space technology or quantum engineering. The smallest atom can travel in space as quantum technology up to the 1st sky zenith direction from planet Earth.[1-8]

Ancestors, dead people, or pitrus want to stay, as in the upper sky or heaven there will be the presence of stable oxygen and its isotopes. This is possible only through

space technology and quantum technology. Thus, for transportation from lower sky to upper sky, there will be a human body sheath or soul to be made with vehicle dynamics.[9-15]

IMPORTANCE OF NETWORK

There will be enough to levitate the human body's sheath, either individually or in a group of networks. Even a single body sheath or soul, can levitate space technology or from quantum technology. There are types of networks, such as series networks of the same species. Ordered from bottom to top, networks assembled as a natural tendency of levitation. All these in a systematic zigzag-manner type of network for levitation of networks for transportation of species from one lower sky to the upper sky through space technology[16-22]

Fig. 1: Network path from lower sky to upper sky (junction point is the sky level as earth planet types)

In the above diagram, the free body diagram, showing the junction meeting point, states that it is the earth planet and upper sky 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and so on. The uppermost is the 1st sky, and the bottommost is the 14th sky. Totally there are 14 skies, 7 upper skies and 7 lower skies.[23-27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Yes, the human body as the best physiological example states that through

space and quantum engineering, one can, in a natural and artificial way, as a network, be transported through vehicles as dynamics. Here one type of species can be able to transport another type of species; this is the natural way of transportation as vehicle dynamics in any network. In these networks millions of species can be transported from lower sky to upper sky.

CONCLUSION

- Bhootas for pick and place to lower the sky of dead persons as soldiers. Here the vehicle itself acts as a physiological vehicle acting as dynamics
- Zenith or upper sky level or other lower sky or nadir sky level is as important as in the case of space technology before and after the life of human beings
- The lower sky at the bottommost is the ghost, and there the vehicle is different; usually made up of sense-level tamarind tree material, it is present.
- This is used for levitation. Not only these lower sky, also asura vehicle is different. In the upper sky, the vehicle for levitation purposes from one sky to another is made as a case of Airavat.
- Ancestors, dead people, or pitrus want to stay, as in the upper sky or heaven there will be the presence of stable oxygen and its isotopes.
- This is possible only through space technology and quantum technology. Thus, for transportation from lower sky to upper sky, there will be a human body sheath or soul to be made with vehicle dynamics
- There are types of networks, such as series networks of the same species. Ordered from bottom to top, networks assembled as a natural tendency of levitation.
- All these in a systematic zigzag-manner type of network for levitation of networks for transportation of species from one lower sky to the upper sky through space technology
- The uppermost is the 1st sky, and the bottommost is the 14th sky. Totally there are 14 skies, 7 upper skies and 7 lower skies
- human body as the best physiological example states that through space and quantum engineering, one can, in a natural and artificial way, as a

network, be transported through vehicles as dynamics.

- Here one type of species can be able to transport another type of species; this is the natural way of transportation as vehicle dynamics in any network. In these networks millions of species can be transported from lower sky to upper sky.

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